

Efficient synthesis of pharmaceutically important fluorinated benzo[*b*]furans[†]

Meenakshi Jain^a and Anjali Tiwari^{b*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, Rajasthan, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, JECRC UDML College of Engineering, Jaipur-302 028, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : at.chem@gmail.com

Manuscript received online 28 January 2013, revised 08 February 2013, accepted 06 April 2013

Abstract : Fluorination of 2-aryloxybenzo[*b*]furans has been successfully accomplished by diethylaminosulfur trifluoride (DAST). Transformation of carbonyl group occurs into difluoromethylene group. All the synthesized compounds have been characterized by elemental analysis and spectral data (IR, ¹H NMR, ¹⁹F NMR and FAB mass). All the synthesized title compounds have also been evaluated for their antibacterial and antifungal activities against *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *A. flavus* and *A. niger*. All the compounds have shown promising results which supports the use of these compounds as a potent antimicrobial agent.

Keywords : Fluorination, 2-aryloxybenzo[*b*]furans, DAST, difluoromethylene, antibacterial and antifungal activities.

Introduction

Benzofurans are widely acclaimed for their antibacterial¹, antifungal¹, analgesic², anti-inflammatory³, antitubercular⁴, anticonvulsant⁵ and antitumor⁶ activities. A number of synthetic methods are available to synthesize the benzofurans⁷⁻¹⁰. Incorporation of fluorine into heterocyclic systems leads to enhance the pharmacological activities of heterocycles^{11,12} and diethylaminosulfur trifluoride (DAST) is one of the highly selective fluorinating reagent for replacing hydroxy groups and carbonyl oxygens with fluorine under very mild and controlled conditions¹³⁻¹⁵. So keeping these observations in mind and in hope to achieve more potent pharmaceutical compounds we have designed new route for the fluorination of 2-aryloxybenzo[*b*]furans with DAST.

Experimental

All the m.p.'s were determined in open glass capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra (ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 557 grating infrared spectrophotometer using KBr pellets. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker spectrophotometer (300 MHz) using CDCl₃ as a solvent. TMS was used as internal standard (chemical shifts were in δ ppm). C₆F₆ was taken

as external standard for ¹⁹F NMR. Mass spectra were recorded on Jeol SX-102 (FAB) mass spectrometer.

*Synthesis of 2-(difluoromethylenearyl)benzo[*b*]furans (2a-f) :*

A solution of DAST (5.0 mmol in 15 mL dry chloroform) was added dropwise in the stirred solution of 2-aryloxybenzo[*b*]furan (5.0 mmol in 15 mL dry chloroform) at 0 °C under nitrogen atmosphere with constant stirring in 15–20 min. It was further stirred at 20 °C till all the starting reactants disappeared from the reaction mixture as shown by TLC. When all the DAST was consumed (after 24 h to 25–30 days), the brown reaction mixture was poured over crushed ice and extracted with chloroform (3 × 50 mL). The extract was then washed with saturated solution of sodium carbonate (3 × 50 mL) followed by water (3 × 50 mL). After drying over sodium sulphate, chloroform was removed under reduced pressure to afford orange coloured residue which was purified by column chromatography over silica gel as adsorbent and benzene : pet. ether (4 : 1) as solvent system to give yellow fluffy title compounds. All the title compounds were synthesized in a similar manner. Their physical, analytical and spectral data are given in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. Schematic presentation is given in Scheme 1.

[†]Dedicated to late Professor V. N. Pathak.

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of 2-(difluoromethylenearyl)benzo[*b*]furans (**2a-f**)

Compd.	X	Molecular formula	Molecular weight	m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) : Calcd. (Found)		
						C	H	F
2a	4-F	C ₁₅ H ₉ OF ₃	262	150–152	68	68.70	3.43	21.75
						(68.65)	(3.40)	(21.66)
2b	4-F; 3-CH ₃	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ OF ₃	276	163–165	70	69.56	3.98	20.65
						(69.50)	(3.90)	(20.74)
2c	2-F; 5-CH ₃	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ OF ₃	276	171–172	56	69.56	3.98	20.65
						(69.51)	(3.95)	(20.74)
2d	4-F; 3-Cl	C ₁₅ H ₈ OCIF ₃	296.5	177–178	55	60.70	2.69	19.22
						(60.66)	(2.63)	(19.10)
2e	4-F; 2-Cl	C ₁₅ H ₈ OCIF ₃	296.5	182–184	62	60.70	2.69	19.22
						(60.65)	(2.67)	(19.20)
2f	2-F; 5-Cl	C ₁₅ H ₈ OCIF ₃	296.5	166–167	61	60.70	2.69	19.22
						(60.68)	(2.64)	(19.18)

Table 2. Spectral data of 2-(difluoromethylenearyl)benzo[*b*]furans (**2a-f**)

Compd.	IR (KBr) ν_{\max} (cm ⁻¹)	¹ H NMR (CDCl ₃) (δ ppm) ^b	MS FAB <i>m/z</i> (M ⁺ + 1)	¹⁹ F NMR (δ ppm) ^c
2a	1135 (C-O-C str.), 1270 (C-F)	7.25–8.35 (9H, m, Ar-H)	263	-101.53 (s, 4-F, 1F), -124.62 (d, CF ₂ , 2F)
	2b	1140 (C-O-C str.), 1260 (C-F)	2.24 (3H, s, CH ₃), 7.04–8.14 (8H, m, Ar-H)	277
2c		1145 (C-O-C str.), 1250 (C-F)	2.25 (3H, s, CH ₃), 7.08–8.16 (8H, m, Ar-H)	277
	2d	1143 (C-O-C str.), 1265 (C-F)	7.26–8.38 (8H, m, Ar-H)	297/299 ^d
2e		1142 (C-O-C str.), 1260 (C-F)	7.23–8.32 (8H, m, Ar-H)	297/299 ^d
	2f	1140 (C-O-C str.), 1265 (C-F)	7.28–8.38 (8H, m, Ar-H)	297/299 ^d

^aDue to isotopic cluster, ^bTMS taken as internal standard, ^cC₆F₆ taken as external standard.

Results and discussion

In the IR spectra of title compounds, disappearance of the carbonyl absorption bands from the region of 1670–1600 cm⁻¹ supports the transformation into 2-(difluoromethylenearyl)benzo[*b*]furans **2** by DAST. The appearance of very strong absorption bands in the region of 1275–1200 cm⁻¹ revealed the presence of C–F bonds. The etheral linkage C–O–C, remains unchanged in the region of 1145–1130 cm⁻¹.

¹H NMR spectra of **2** exhibit multiplets in the region of δ 7.12–8.34 ppm due to the presence of aromatic protons. The presence of fluorine was confirmed by the ¹⁹F

NMR spectra. The fluorine attached to the phenyl ring in **2**, appeared in the region of δ -105.621 to -109.621 ppm as a singlet and the new singlet observed in the region of -124.35 to -124.75 ppm was described due to transformation of carbonyl group into difluoromethylene group.

In the FAB mass spectra of title compounds the molecular ion peaks [M]⁺ are in harmony with their structures which confirms the formation of title compounds.

Antimicrobial activities :

All the synthesized title compounds were screened for their antibacterial activity against Gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and Gram-negative bacteria *Es-*

Table 3. Antibacterial activity of 2-(difluoromethylenearyl)benzo[*b*]furans (**2a-f**)

Compd.	Mean value of area of inhibition in mm (1000 ppm) IZ (AI)		Mean value of area of inhibition in mm (800 ppm) IZ (AI)		Mean value of area of inhibition in mm (400 ppm) IZ (AI)	
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
	Streptomycin	11.8	10.6	10.0	9.2	8.8
2a	10.0 (0.84)	9.1 (0.85)	8.7 (0.87)	8.0 (0.86)	6.9 (0.78)	5.8 (0.76)
2b	11.4 (0.96)	10.3 (0.97)	9.7 (0.97)	9.2 (1.00)	8.5 (0.96)	7.1 (0.93)
2c	11.6 (0.98)	10.0 (0.94)	9.6 (0.96)	8.9 (0.96)	8.3 (0.94)	7.6 (1.00)
2d	10.7 (0.90)	9.8 (0.92)	8.9 (0.89)	8.5 (0.92)	8.1 (0.92)	7.4 (0.97)
2e	10.2 (0.86)	9.4 (0.88)	9.5 (0.95)	8.2 (0.89)	7.8 (0.88)	7.1 (0.93)
2f	10.8 (0.91)	9.5 (0.89)	9.1 (0.91)	8.1 (0.88)	8.0 (0.90)	6.8 (0.89)

IZ = Inhibition area (zone) excluding diameter of disk.

AI = (Activity index) = Inhibition area of sample/inhibition area of standard.

Table 4. Antifungal activity of 2-(difluoromethylenearyl)benzo[*b*]furans (**2a-f**)

Compd.	Mean value of area of inhibition in mm (1000 ppm) IZ (AI)		Mean value of area of inhibition in mm (800 ppm) IZ (AI)		Mean value of area of inhibition in mm (400 ppm) IZ (AI)	
	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
	Mycostatin	12.2	11.4	11.5	10.0	9.7
2a	10.5 (0.86)	9.9 (0.86)	10.2 (0.88)	8.5 (0.85)	7.1 (0.73)	6.8 (0.80)
2b	11.8 (0.96)	10.5 (0.92)	11.4 (0.99)	9.3 (0.93)	9.0 (0.92)	7.2 (0.84)
2c	11.2 (0.91)	10.1 (0.88)	10.7 (0.93)	10.0 (1.00)	8.6 (0.88)	7.8 (0.91)
2d	9.3 (0.76)	9.5 (0.83)	9.3 (0.80)	9.1 (0.91)	8.3 (0.85)	6.0 (0.70)
2e	9.8 (0.80)	10.1 (0.88)	9.8 (0.85)	8.7 (0.87)	7.4 (0.76)	5.9 (0.69)
2f	10.9 (0.89)	8.8 (0.77)	10.9 (0.94)	8.4 (0.84)	6.9 (0.71)	6.3 (0.81)

IZ = Inhibition area (zone) excluding diameter of disk.

AI = (Activity index) = Inhibition area of sample/inhibition area of standard.

cherichia coli at 200, 400 and 800 ppm concentration. Antifungal activity was done against *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus* at 200, 400 and 800 ppm concentration. Streptomycin and mycostatin were used as standard drugs

for antibacterial and antifungal evaluations, respectively. Compounds were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal efficacy following the inhibition zone technique¹⁶ and results are tabulated in Tables 3 and 4, respectively.

Scheme 1

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Deputy Director and Head, SAIF, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow (India) and Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur (India) for elemental analyses and spectral (IR, ¹H NMR, ¹⁹F NMR and FAB mass) data. Authors are also thankful to UGC (Bhopal) for the sanction of MRP.

References

1. K. Shivakumar, S. Reddy, P. Vithal and M. B. Halli, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2008, **61**, 2274.
2. S. Radl, P. Hezky, J. Urbankova, P. Vachal and I. Krejcf, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 2000, **65**, 280.
3. V. B. Jadhav, M. V. Kulkarni, V. P. Rasal, S. S. Biradar and M. D. Vinay, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2008, **43**, 1721.
4. K. Manna, Y. K. Agarwal and K. K. Srinivasan, *Indian J. Het. Chem.*, 2008, **2**, 87.
5. H. J. Patel, J. Sarra, F. Caruso, M. Rossi, U. Doshi and R. A. Stephani, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2006, **16**, 4644.
6. I. Hayakawa, R. Shioya, T. Agatsuma, H. Furukawa and Y. Sugano, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2004, **14**, 3411.
7. S. E. Denmark, R. C. Smith, W. T. T. Chang and J. M. Muhuhi, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **131**, 3104.
8. F. Contiero, K. M. Jones, E. A. Matts, A. Porzelle and N. C. O. Tomkinson, *Synlett*, 2009, **18**, 3003.
9. J. R. Wang and K. Manabe, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2010, **75**, 5340.
10. T. Pei, C.-Y. Chen, L. DiMichele and I. W. Davies, *Org. Lett.*, 2010, **12**, 4972.
11. Ann. M. Thayer, *Chem. Engg. News*, 2006, **84**, 15.
12. D. O'Hagan, C. Schaffrath, S. L. Cobb, John T. G. Hamilton and C. D. Murphy, *Nature*, 2002, **416**, 279.
13. S. D'Errico, G. Oliviero, N. Borbone, J. Amato, D. D'Alonzo, V. Piccialli, L. Mayol and G. Piccialli, *Molecules*, 2012, **17**, 13036.
14. M. Baumann, I. R. Baxendale and S. V. Ley, *Synlett*, 2008, **14**, 2111.
15. M. Hudlicky, *Org. React.*, 1988, **35**, 513.
16. M. C. Bryant, "Antibiotics and their Laboratory Control", Butterworths, London, 1968, 26.